

A Free Flow Between Becomings and Becoming Imperceptible— Rare, but Possible

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“[W]e bathe in delirium,” Gilles Deleuze (2001, p. 43) says in *Pure Immanence: Essays on A Life*, asserting that “history presents us with a most peculiar phenomenon: the reactive forces triumph ... [and] Everywhere we see the victory of No over Yes, of reaction over action” (pp. 74-75). And because of this he thinks that “[l]ife becomes adaptive and regulative” (p. 75) and that we no longer understand what it means to become imperceptible, that is, creative—the restless inhabitant of imperceptible becoming. Such insights concerning the darker sides of life, or what he called the overwhelming reactive forces, the sadness of life, which he had developed earlier in his *Nietzsche and Philosophy* (1983a), suggest that he had given up on the hope that the whole human species would make a free flow between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible possible. Does this suggest that he gave up the hope that specific individuals can make such a free flow possible in education and society at large? I do not think so. I argue that his writings suggest that a free flow between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible is possible, and that this flow requires a recognition of active and reactive forces as well as a regulation of reactive forces through thinking (Deleuze, 1994), something a post-humanist such as Rosi Braidotti does not acknowledge to any great extent. On the contrary, she focuses one-sidedly on the affirmation of active forces, asserting that there is a way out of the reactive; she even claims that it is possible to remove reactive forces. I argue that such a one-sided view is naïve and does not support a free flow between becomings and imperceptible becoming; it misrecognises reactive forces, and leads to a one-sided view of affirmation, joy, and happiness, and to dead-end utopias such as the one suggested by Nathan Snaza and John A. Weaver (2015).

Deleuze, who warns about such tendencies mentioned above, affirmed not merely the value, but also the possibility of and hope for a free flow between becoming perceptible and becoming imperceptible. He also expresses, inter alia, in his latest book, the woeful examples of people becoming slaves through education and in societies by repeating the flow of cases forged by “fictive causal chains, illegitimate rules [and the] simulacra of belief ... [through] simple verbal repetition that only simulates its effect” (Deleuze, 2001, p. 42). Such forces will, according to Deleuze, not merely make any individual or group fall into present concerns and maintain them as if these should be upheld, but will also make people believe that they have to try to solve issues or problems under already more or less given conditions, without necessarily changing these conditions or the way issues and problems are understood. In order to oppose such moves, Deleuze argues for the importance of acting upon our freedom to respond responsibly to chains of constraining conditions through thinking.¹ Such a response is, for him, not about moving beyond

¹ Even though Deleuze portrays, via Friedrich Nietzsche, the historical conditions for freedom in not very positive terms, he is optimistic about the possibility that at least some people can move away from constraining chains, and find their ways anew—themes that we also see cropping up in Hannah Arendt and Immanuel Kant, although in different ways; see also Allen W. Wood (2014), who argues, through Immanuel Kant, Johan Gottlieb Fichte, Karl Marx and Georg Wilhelm

reactive forces or about a transition from becoming perceptible to becoming imperceptible; it is rather about a free flow or play or moving between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible. Such moves are, for Deleuze, not easily actualised, at least not in relation to powerful reactive forces such as *ressentiment* and bad conscience, which he thinks diminish the possibility of becoming imperceptible or even triumph over it. Both of these can weigh one down, and make it hard to find one's way again, according to him. For example, *ressentiment* separates the active force from what it can do, that is, from bursting creativity, and, when this is the case, the separation leads, for Deleuze, to an inability to respect and love, to the imputation of wrongs to the other, even to the need to view the other as evil. It can then make those concerned oppose "themselves to active forces and represent themselves as superior" (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 123), and even hide their "hatred under a tempting love: I who accuse you, it is for your own good; I love you in order that you will join me, until you are joined with me, until you yourself become a painful, sick, reactive being, a good being" (1983a, p. 128). A sign of this is when the other has its conscience being poisoned and becomes the slave of its slavishness. *Ressentiment* then becomes a powerful reactive force, together with bad conscience; that is, when, through projection, it has made the other responsible for whatever it is that caused the situation, and the other cries, "It is my fault, it is my fault" (1983a, p. 132). When this happens, *ressentiment* makes one hostile towards the other; it creates a sense of jealousy and of inferiority towards the other, and makes one believe that one's presumed inferiority justifies one's actions towards the other, and that one can do what one wants with the other, instead of engaging in becoming imperceptible and making it possible for the other to do the same. It even fuels shame and guilt on the part of the other; the other can, then, feel so overwhelmed by negative emotions that he/she feels at a loss, even becomes invisible, that is, diminished to the point that he or she loses him- or herself, at times even completely. Reactive forces have then triumphed over active forces.

In my view, shame and guilt can be related not merely to negativity, but also to what could be done in a positive sense, something that Deleuze does not seem to consider.¹ He says, for example, that

Friedrich Hegel, for the free development of each in the various relations they encounter. Hence, as constrained beings, people are not just slaves to present conditions, even though, at times, it is so or may feel so; they are free, or at least capable of acting upon the idea of freedom, in relation to conditions that limit their freedom. So, we see that Deleuze is in good company when it comes to acknowledging constraining conditions, while at the same time recognizing the value of freedom, even though he does so in a somewhat different way than, inter alia, Arendt and Kant.

¹ Stanley Cavell, for example, views shame and guilt not merely in relation to disgust or disdain, but also as "a call for a transformation of things, and before all a transformation of the self" (1990, p. 46); the latter is, as I argue, through the voice of Cavell, "a return to philosophy" (Roth, 2010, p. 396), and to the possibility of finding one's way again. See also Kant (1996) when he says that conscience is the "*internal court* in man ('before which his thoughts accuse or excuse one another')" (p. 203/AA 6: p. 438) (here and elsewhere in this article, references to Kant cite page numbers from the English translation followed by volume and page number from the German *Akademie-Ausgabe* edition of Kant's works. "Translations of Kant's works commonly include volume and page numbers of the Academy Edition. References to the Academy Edition often use 'AA' for *Akademie-Ausgabe*" ["Further Reading," in Kant 2017, p. xxxii]). Here Kant treats conscience as a crucial aspect of our duty to engage in self-examination and self-knowledge. It should remind us of our duty to engage in the pursuit of coming to "*know* (scrutinize, fathom)

humanity's "only hope lies in a revolutionary becoming: the only way of casting off ... shame or responding to what is intolerable" (1995, p. 171). Here we see that, even though Deleuze seems to say that shame is potentially productive, it is more a question of a casting of shame than of being reminded of what can be done through shame in a constructive sense.¹ That is, if one lets shame weigh oneself down, then it is not constructive, but if, for example, shame is related to what one could do, that is, to becoming imperceptible, then it does not weigh one down. It becomes, instead, an active force. Nonetheless, even though Deleuze does not seem to recognise that conscience can work both ways, he is clear about the dangers of not encountering the above-mentioned forces responsibly through thinking, and of believing that there is a way out of reactive forces. Such thoughts open up, for Deleuze, not merely to a disintegration of the various possible becomings, but also to fictional ideas such as dead-end utopias. He also thinks that these ideas open the door to reactive forces that diminish our freedom to find our way again.² It is therefore risky, even dangerous, that a post-humanist such as Braidotti, who draws on the work of Deleuze, focuses so one-sidedly on the affirmation of various becomings, joy and the vital force of life—Zoe—without paying enough attention to the value of also encountering and regulating reactive forces, which Deleuze, through Friedrich Nietzsche, emphasises.³ Even though she says that she wants to

yourself" (Kant, 2017, p. 206/AA 6: p. 441). Hence, Kant treats conscience as a morally motivating feeling, leading either to negativity or to positivity, that is, either to a feeling that weighs one down or to a feeling that awakens one to one's responsibility to find one's way again or, in Kant's own words, to a moral feeling that awakens one's duty to improve oneself morally. Conscience, for Kant, is therefore not necessarily bad; it can be seen also as a reminder of our duty to do what the moral law requires, even demands, of us.

¹ Aislinn O'Donnell (2017), for example, defends a view of shame in the writings of Deleuze that focuses more on casting shame off, instead of viewing it as a force that also can be understood as a reminder of what can be done in a more positive sense. Even Sjoerd van Tuinen (2014), who talks about Deleuze's writings on shame and guilt, does not draw attention to how shame and guilt can be a call for transformation and/or a reminder of our duty to scrutinize ourselves.

² See Deleuze (2001), and his book on Nietzsche and his philosophy (1983a, in particular Chapters 2 and 4), in which he continuously comes back to the idea that reactive forces triumph over the active; in this book, Deleuze (1983a) also argues that "an active force *becomes reactive* (in a new sense) when reactive forces (in the first sense) separate it from what it can do" (p. 57). When this happens, an active force is "dragged into the abyss and turned against itself" (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 67), thereby hindering it to "produce a burst of creativity" (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 111). However, it is not just a case of an active force being separated from what it can do; it is also dangerous to offer more or less easy ways out of reactive forces, since doing so misrecognises the strength of reactive forces, thereby contaminating the active.

³ See for example, Braidotti (2006; 2011; 2018; 2019), in which she somewhat surprisingly focuses merely on affirming the vital force of Zoe, but not on finding a balance between active and reactive forces in a developed sense. It is also surprising that Ian Buchanan, in edited books such as *A Deleuzian Century?* (1999) and *Deleuze and the Contemporary World* (2006), edited together with Adrian Parr, does not draw attention to Deleuze's call for encountering both active and reactive forces. Sjoerd van Tuinen (2014), however, draws some attention to active and reactive forces, and to the reactive triumphing over the active. Unfortunately, Van Tuinen (2014) merely mentions

replace what she calls the negativity of reactive forces with “Spinoza’s ethics of joyful affirmation” (2013, p. 343), without dismissing “the reality of conflict and pain” (2019, p. 154), she does not encounter reactive forces thoroughly, nor how these can be regulated. On the contrary, she says, naively, that “the pursuit of an ethics of joyful affirmation” (2019, p. 72) not only takes the “negative elements ... seriously” (2019, p. 154), but also removes “the barriers of negativity” (2018, p. 221) and “offers a way out of the state of exhaustion, anxiety and fear” (2019, p. 154), not merely at a particular time, but eternally.

Hence, even though it seems that she would not want to dismiss reactive forces, she also asserts that there is a way out of them, and that they can be removed, and stopped from having a negative impact on ourselves. Such a one-sided and blind emphasis on “an ethics of joyful affirmation,” with its stress on “a way out” and on “removing” reactive forces, misrecognises the strength of such forces. As such it opens the gates to dark waters such as fictional utopian ideals of a coming perfect world in which human beings are supposed to experience the fruits of becomings, such as the ones expressed by Braidotti, in terms of affirmation, joy and happiness. The naïve stress on the above-mentioned ethics has even led educational post-humanists such as Snaza and Weaver (2015) to express not merely their wish or hope, but also the promise that posthumanism—with its one-sided emphasis on joyful affirmation—will provide us with “a general direction for an evolutionary development of culture” (p. xi), one that will take us back to the Garden of Eden.¹

the importance of the “becoming-active of the reactive forces that have constituted us, the transmutation of our inherited sentiments such as *ressentiment* and bad conscience” (p. 98), without tackling the idea of striving to find a balance between active and reactive forces through thinking. Finding such a balance is, however, not an easy matter. There is also a certain degree of indeterminacy in deciding on it, despite all available evidence, due to, inter alia, the inscrutability of reference, that is, that words and objects/actions can be connected in various ways, and that we cannot know in each and every case—with certainty—which way is right (see, for example, Donald Davidson [1997] for a discussion on such matters). Moreover, as Paul Guyer (2020) writes, “there is nothing that can guarantee that a free will is always a good will, so nothing that can guarantee that even the most carefully chosen leaders [nor anyone else] will do the right thing.” And he continues, “Even the best institutions only make justice possible, not necessary—the human will can pervert anything” (p. 334). Additionally, people can also deceive the other or themselves that they are trying to find, for example, a balance somewhere in the middle between active and reactive forces, while they in fact are not (see, for example, Donald Davidson [2004], Eric Funkhouser [2019], Clancy Martin [2009] and Laura Papish [2018] for discussions on deception and self-deception). Nonetheless, despite all concerns, it is still of value to pursue or at least to strive to pursue a balance between active and reactive forces, since the opposite is not a reasonable option; it suggests that one give up one’s indefinite individuality of life, to use Deleuze’s words.

¹ Although such images may be appealing, experience shows us that the whole human species has not come back to the Garden of Eden. Moreover, as Moses Mendelssohn (1983) says, “you will find no steady progress in ... [the] development [of the human species] that brings it ever closer to perfection,” nor back to the promised land; despite the lack of such experiences, it happens, according to him, that “a dot blazes up in the midst of the great mass, [and] becomes a glittering star” (pp. 96-97). Such insights by Mendelssohn are, unfortunately, not reflected in the work by Snaza and Weaver, nor in the work by Braidotti. Moreover, even though some human beings can

None of them, therefore, undertakes the task of regulating reactive forces through thinking.¹ It is therefore problematic that the above-mentioned authors focus so narrowly on just one of two forces which are, for Deleuze, inseparable. Deleuze also argues that the denial of the vital balance between the above forces drags us down into the abyss of evaluating others and ourselves in relation to the extent to which we pursue various specific ends such as the dead-end utopias mentioned above, with their one-sided stress on affirmation and joy. It is, for him, not a simple case of experiencing joy when moving between various becomings. Such moves can also fuel frustration, anxiety, fear, despair and loss. It is not even the case that moves between perceptible and imperceptible becomings necessarily lead to an experience of happiness; such moves can be overwhelming and terrifying, and lead to disorder and chaos, apart from transformations over time; this can be seen in science, philosophy and art as well as in other ways of life, in particular when people come up with something new and original which may constitute an example of a work of genius.² People can respond in negative ways to that which stands as an example of originality, and it can take years before such a work is recognised as original; this is due to the fact that people do not necessarily and in each and every case want to disturb and destabilise that what they believe, which when it happens can frustrate and even lead to loss and despair; it may even be the case that they avoid opening the gates to territories unknown to them, for fear of doing so. Their responses can, therefore, be an expression of reactive forces in relation to that which at some point can be recognised as original and as an example of genius. Additionally, it is not clear whether Braidotti thinks that her suggested path to the affirmation of joy necessarily concerns the whole human species or all species as such, or whether it concerns what Deleuze called the indefinite individuality of life. Nor is it clear whether Braidotti thinks that there is a sure way of arousing and maintaining an ethics of joyful affirmation over time, a becoming which Deleuze (1995) does not think is possible to arouse or maintain consistently over time; such issues ought to be clarified.

Apart from what has been said above, Deleuze also thinks that a misrecognition of the power of reactive forces has led to more or less modern philosophical and fictional ideas concerning, *inter alia*, the possibility for human beings to render themselves autonomous in each and every situation

become “glittering stars,” there is no guarantee that they will continue to be such creatures. On the contrary, human beings can oscillate between active and reactive forces and backslide—even wilfully—from the pursuit of an ethics of joyful affirmation (see also note 3, p. 112 above).

¹ Donna Haraway (2016), for example, also points out the dangers of not staying with specific troubles. She argues that when one does not do so, one can be led to either utopian (or dystopian) thoughts (as in the case of Snaza and Weaver), or to naïve views of finding a way out of reactive forces (as in the case of Braidotti).

² See Deleuze and Guattari (1994), in particular their final chapter “Conclusion: From Chaos to the Brain,” in which they argue that neither art, science, nor philosophy can avoid chaos completely; these faculties can, however, “return from the land of the dead” (p. 202) by creating something new and original. Hence, even though Braidotti seems to think that she can avoid chaos entirely by offering a way to joy and happiness, it is, for Deleuze and Guattari, not possible to avoid chaos, other than temporarily, and through hard and creative work.

through the use of their understanding and reason, something that Deleuze disputes.¹ He thinks that we cannot control reactive forces effectively. A reason for this is, for Deleuze, that the unconscious and constitutive synthesis of habits is so strong that we cannot control reactive forces completely.² Another reason is that Deleuze together with Guattari believes that the above-mentioned formation of habits is shaped and disciplined under the conditions of the capitalist market.³ They think this market shapes and controls our images and directs our desire towards them instead of encouraging a free flow between perceptible and imperceptible becoming. Deleuze (1994) thinks, therefore, that it is just a fiction that we can control our actions effectively in each and every situation. Such a disconcerting view does not, however, suggest, for him, that we are slaves under the above-mentioned conditions. On the contrary, he believes that we can react and respond responsibly to flows of habitual reactive behaviour through thinking, and this we can do, according to him, by increasing our powers of thinking by affirming such a good mode

¹ Deleuze criticizes Kant's ideas of autonomy. He thinks that Kant does not pay enough attention to challenges people encounter when they try to render themselves autonomous. Kant, however, was aware of the challenges that human beings face when they try to render themselves autonomous; see, for example, his *Religion within the Boundaries of Mere Reason* (1998b), in which he discusses human beings' innate propensity to radical evil; this is a book Deleuze did not pay much attention to. In it, Kant (1998b) argues that it is hard work to regulate what he called our innate propensity to radical evil, and that it would require "a *revolution* in the disposition of the human being ... so a 'new man' can come about only through a kind of rebirth, as it were a new creation" (p. 68/AA 6: p. 47). Although Kant (1986b) thinks it would require such a revolution, he raises the question whether such a new man ever could come about. He says: "[I]f a human being is corrupt in the very ground of his maxims, how can he possibly bring about this revolution by his own forces and become a good human being on his own?" (p. 68/AA 6: p. 47). He seeks to resolve these seemingly incompatible views about human beings in his *Religion within the Boundaries of Mere Reason*, namely the views that they can and should render themselves autonomous, on the one hand, and that they have an innate propensity to radical evil, which corrupts their duty to render themselves autonomous, on the other. Kant's way of resolving the issue with above-mentioned views is to turn to religion, in particular Christianity. He argues that human beings have to turn to Christianity in order to fulfill their duty to comply with the moral law, since they cannot expect to fulfill their duty on their own, due to their innate propensity to radical evil. Moses Mendelssohn, however, questioned whether Christianity is the only organized religion that can serve as a vehicle for good; see also Paul Guyer (2020) for a discussion on this and similar issues. Whether Kant succeeds in solving the above-mentioned and seemingly incompatible views is also philosophically questionable; see Stephen R. Palmquist (2016, in particular Parts III and IV), Lawrence R. Pasternack (2014, in particular Chapters 5 and 6) and Allen W. Wood (1999, in particular Chapter 9, and 1970, in particular Chapters 5 and 6), for discussions on Kant's views on human beings' duty to render themselves autonomous, and on evil, religion and the Church; also, on whether Kant succeeds in solving the seemingly incompatible views about human beings.

² Our consciousness is for Deleuze a slave of the unconsciousness; in this he is echoing the words of David Hume (1978, p. 415), who argued that reason is the slave of our passions.

³ See Deleuze and Guattari (1987; 2013).

of existence.¹ When we do so, there is, for him, an opening for “an impersonal and yet singular life that releases a pure event freed from the accidents of internal and external life” (Deleuze, 2001, p. 28). Such an opening instantiates an affirmation of a vital form of life, namely the “singularization: a life of pure immanence” (2001, p. 29), which, for him, also opens the door to joy and not to sadness, and to the possibility of becoming new anew. It signifies, moreover, a responsible response towards reactive behaviour (at least for the moment), and “a liberation of thought from those images which imprison it” (Deleuze, 1994, p. xv), that is, from dogmatic thought. It also exemplifies the value of the freedom of moving between different perceptible becomings such as becoming woman, mother, friend, doctor etc., as well as between perceptible becoming *and* becoming imperceptible in an affirmative and joyful dance, in which the active forces are affirmed and the power of the reactive ones are regulated through thinking.² Such a world in which thinking is recaptured marks, for Deleuze, a good mode of existence, in which the process of thinking is open-ended and never-ending; it is a regulative ideal toward which we can move while not fully attaining it.³

The above-mentioned doubleness of becoming suggests, however, that it is not merely moves between already perceptible identities, but also consists of flights that go beyond those more or less fixed identities to that which is not yet, to an affirmation of an infinite flow of newness.⁴ Such moves instantiate flights beyond perceptible becomings to that which is yet to come, to something new. Such a becoming is not, for Deleuze and Guattari (1987), a “correspondence between relations... [nor] is it a resemblance, an imitation, or, at the limit, an identification” (p. 237). It is neither a “progress or regress along a series ..., [it does not] occur in the imagination ... [and it is]

¹ See, for example, Deleuze (1983b, pp. 22-25). Kant (1988b) also thinks that it is a continuous challenge for people to regulate their inclinations and raise themselves above constraining conditions; see also Guyer (2009) for a discussion on this and similar issues.

² See Arendt (2003) and Kant (2000, pp. 174-175/AA 5: p. 294; 2006, pp. 122-124/AA § 59 [7: pp. 226-229]; 2007, pp. 445-446/AA 9: p. 451) for similar arguments concerning the value of thinking; see also for Arendt (2006; 1968, in particular Chapters 12 and 13), and Kant (1998b) for discussions on what can happen when people do not think for themselves, etc. This tendency not to think for oneself cannot merely lead to dogmatic thought, as Deleuze claims, or to totalitarianism in power, as Arendt claims; it can also fuel the three grades of evil, as Kant would claim, namely, the frailty of our will, our liability to deceive others and ourselves, and our capacity to exterminate the other, none of which promotes thinking for oneself or from the standpoint of the other; and it happens constantly. See also Klas Roth (2018; 2019) for discussions that education, as it stands, does not necessarily promote thinking in the-above mentioned Kantian sense.

³ See also Guyer (2014), which argues that Cavell and Kant argue for a similar position, namely that thinking in moral education is never-ending and never ended; see also Roth (2014) for a related standpoint about the process of education.

⁴ See also Kant (2006) which claims that “what can be made of the human being [and] what he is prepared to make of himself” (p. 185/[AA 7: p. 285]) is dependent upon whether he acts upon the idea of freedom or not, which indicates something similar to what Deleuze expresses, namely, that what human beings can become is dependent upon what they are prepared to become through freedom in education and society at large.

not an evolution, at least not an evolution by descent and filiation” (p. 238). It means, for Deleuze (2007a), “never to imitate, nor to ‘do like’, nor to conform to a model, whether it’s of justice or of truth,” and he continues, “There is no terminus from which you set out, none which you arrive at or which you ought to arrive at” (p. 2). Becomings are, for him, therefore “not phenomena of imitation or assimilation, but of a double capture...” (p. 2). This doubleness suggests, moreover, that it is not just a case of moving between various perceptible becomings without becoming imperceptible, since such a one-sided view of becoming diminishes the freedom to engage in thinking and leads to wandering in deserts of illusions such as those expressed by Snaza and Weaver. If, however, people do try to find a balance between the above-mentioned becomings, then it is also possible to move beyond perceptible becomings and engage in lines of flight that have “no beginning or end” (Deleuze, 2007a, p. 30). Such flights are for him, therefore, not a part

of history; [since] history amounts only the set of preconditions, however recent, that one leaves behind in order to “become,” that is, to create something new. (Deleuze, 1995, p. 171)

Such flights are, for him, creative, and societies that make it possible for those concerned to encounter them are characterised not so much by their reactive forces, nor by their contradictions, but by their flights to horizons, something Deleuze believes happens in philosophy, literature, and science when the free flow between the doubleness of becoming is made possible.¹ However, the free flow or dance implies, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), not merely a movement between perceptible becomings and imperceptible becoming, but it also implies the inevitability of chaos, a chaos that “undoes every consistency in the infinite” (p. 42), which can be a difficult experience. This is because it is a move away from ourselves, our specific identities, and when this happens, we find ourselves wandering in deserts “populated by tribes, flora and fauna” (Deleuze, 2007b, p. 11), and sometimes in despair before we can find our way again and become filled with hope for the possibility of flights beyond that which is already known to that which has no beginning nor end. However, as we have seen, even though Deleuze in some of his earlier writings may have had the hope that such societies could come about, he became more doubtful, perhaps even more despondent, in his hope for the possibility that the whole human species could become imperceptible. Some of Deleuze’s darker views can, however, also be seen earlier on, as when he talks about control societies, and says

People are of course constantly talking about prisons, schools, hospitals: the institutions are breaking down. But they’re breaking down because they’re fighting a losing battle. New kinds of punishment, education, health care are being stealthily introduced. (Deleuze, 1995, pp. 174-175)

Or when he says

Educational reforms, industrial reforms, hospital, army, prison reforms ... everyone knows these institutions are in more or less terminal decline. It’s simply a matter of nursing them through their death throes and keeping people busy until the new forces

¹ See Deleuze (1995, p. 171), and also Deleuze (2007b), in which he argues that “philosophy is a discipline that is just as inventive, just as creative as any other discipline, and it consists in creating or inventing concepts” (p. 318).

knocking at the door take over. (Deleuze, 1995, p. 178)

The passages above seem to suggest that even though there are examples of what he calls becoming imperceptible or lines of flight in societies, Deleuze came to believe that it is a lost battle for the whole human species, something Braidotti does not seem to believe in with her emphasis on a way out of reactive forces. This is so not merely because people get caught in reactive behaviour and more or less troublesome separations between active and reactive forces, but also because of all that which, according to Deleuze and Guattari (1994), threatens thinking, such as “stupidity, forgetfulness, aphasia, delirium, madness” (p. 52). Deleuze and Guattari also think that “thought [can be] threatened less by error than by [the] inevitable illusions that come from within reason” (p. 52), something Deleuze thinks Immanuel Kant eloquently has shown in his three critiques.¹ Another reason for this doubt is the lack of examples of becoming imperceptible when it comes to the whole human species. However, and as seen from the above, Deleuze believes that even though there are rare flights of becoming imperceptible, these are not overwhelming or strong enough to combat reactive forces as such. Hence, Deleuze seems to have given up on the belief that the human species as a whole can become imperceptible. He also believes that we do not even have a “sure way of maintaining becomings, or still more of arousing them, even within ourselves” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 173);² this is because we cannot know with certainty how to go on in each and every situation, according to Deleuze (Deleuze, 1983a, p. 58); it is more a question of engaging in the difficult art of thinking. Nonetheless, such dark views about the whole human species’ potential for becoming imperceptible do not suggest that he had given up on the possibility of examples of creativity, of becoming imperceptible, for specific individuals.³ On the contrary. It

¹ See Deleuze (2008), in which he discusses the three critiques of Kant, namely *Critique of the Power of Judgment* (2000); *Critique of Pure Reason* (1998a); *Critique of Practical Reason* (1997); see also Craig Lundy and Daniela Voss (2015, in particular Chapters 1-4) for critical discussions on Deleuze interpretation of Kant’s philosophy as it is expressed in his three critiques.

² See also Kant (1998b), who argued that “the depths of his own heart (the subjective first ground of his maxims) are to him inscrutable” (p. 71/AA 6: p. 51). People cannot, therefore, be certain of how to comply with the moral law, nor how they can maintain it. See also Kant’s comments on ends that are also duties in his *Metaphysics of Morals* (2017, pp. 160-170/AA, 6: pp. 386-6: 398), namely on our duties to perfect ourselves and the happiness of others, which for Kant, are wide, and therefore do not specify how or when to perfect ourselves and make others happy. Kant says, for example, that no “rational principle prescribes specifically *how* far one should go in cultivating one’s capacities (in enlarging or correcting one’s capacity for understanding, i.e., in acquiring knowledge or skill)” (Kant, 2017, p.165/AA 6: p. 392), nor does such a principle prescribe specifically how one can go about helping others to become happy. Additionally, the fulfillment of such principles is, for Kant, meritorious, “but failure to fulfill them is not in itself *culpability*” (Kant, 2017, p. 164/AA, 6: p. 390).

³ The question, however, about whether the whole of humankind or individuals are progressing is not new. It was also discussed between Moses Mendelssohn and Immanuel Kant, where Mendelssohn (1983) says, “Now, as far as human race as a whole is concerned, you will find no steady progress in its development that brings it ever closer to perfection. Rather do we see the human race in its totality slightly oscillate; it never took a few steps forward without soon afterwards, and with redoubled speed, sliding back to its previous position.... Individual man

would not merely be a contradiction to claim that there are no such examples and have never been; it would also suggest a lack of recognition and understanding of the obvious examples of creativity in, for example, philosophy, science and art. But this is not what Deleuze expresses. It is rather the other way around. He continuously comes back to the possibility of becoming imperceptible by using examples from philosophy, science and art in education and society at large, and by encouraging thinking. He says, for example,

The task of philosophy when it creates concepts, entities, is always to extract an event from things and beings, to set up the new event from things and beings, always to give them a new event: space, time, matter, thought, the possible as events. (Deleuze and Guattari, 1994, p. 33)

The creation of concepts can then disturb that which is already known and challenge our ways of understanding.¹ Such events can create cracks in that which is known, and throw us into unknown

advances, but mankind continually fluctuates within fixed limits, while maintaining, on the whole, about the same degree of morality in all periods—the same amount of religion and irreligion, of virtue and vice, of felicity and misery; the same result, if one compares like with like; of all these goods and evils as much as is required for the passage of the individual man in order that he might be educated here below, and approach as closely as possible the perfection which is apportioned to him and for which he is destined” (pp. 96-97). Here we see that Mendelssohn was not optimistic about the progression of humankind. Kant (1991), on the other, and against Mendelssohn, asserts that he (Kant) is “permitted to assume that, since the human race is constantly progressing in cultural matters (in keeping with its natural purpose), it is also engaged in progressive improvement in relation to the moral end of its existence. This progress may at times be *interrupted* but never *broken off*.” And he continues, somewhat surprisingly, “I do not need to prove this assumption; it is up to the adversary to prove his case” (p. 88). The discussion between Mendelssohn and Kant had, however, to do with whether Christianity is a more progressive religion than Judaism and whether Christianity would bring “its adherents closer to moral perfection and should be universally adopted for that reason” (Guyer, 2020, p. 324). Kant, who believed that Christianity is the religion that would bring its adherents closer to perfection, did not believe that Judaism would do so. Mendelssohn, by contrast, thought that perfection is possible for individuals, but not for the whole human species, and believed “that the moral truths of the religion of reason always are and always have been available to all people, thus that Christianity should not be regarded as a more progressive religion than Judaism” (Guyer, 2020, p. 324).

¹ See for example Kant (2000), § 9, pp. 102-105/AA 5: pp. 216-219; § 29, pp. 148-160/AA 5: pp. 264-279; § 50, pp. 196-197/AA 5: 319-321, who argues for the value of searching for new ways of thinking, and claims that this can be done by engaging in the free play between imagination and understanding; see also Guyer (2006) for a discussion on various interpretations of such free play, and for his arguments for how it reasonably should be understood. Guyer also argues that we cannot know how to awaken nor sustain such a free play, nor how we can make ourselves creative in a decisive way; he says, “the very concept of the harmony of the faculties as the explanation of our pleasure in beauty requires that our experience of beauty not be constrained by any determinate rules, such characterizations can never offer anything more than some examples of the ways in which our experience of beauty can go beyond the determinate requirements of cognition” (2006, p. 193).

territories, which can disintegrate us, and hence frustrate and create anxiety, even despair.¹ However infrequent, these are tokens of potentials, which, according to Deleuze, should not be ignored, but taken seriously. He thinks that the potential of such tokens demands of us to make perceptible becomings imperceptible, that is, lines of flight toward the indefinite and infinite. Such engagement is, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), not disconnected and disengaged. It is instead connected with that which is already known, which is maintained, reproduced, imitated, and copied in an endless process of repetitive acts. It is an encounter with that which is known, with the urgency of impossible situations, in which questions of immediacy require acts of thinking other than the ones expected; such events are, for Deleuze (2015) “actualized in us, they wait for us and invite us in” (p.153). He believes that such acts can break with that which is already known—from dogmatic images of thought, dead-end utopias, and naïve affirmations of joy and happiness. He also thinks that the singularisation of such acts deterritorialise us and others, and open the door to the possibility of finding one’s way again, a process seemingly open to each and every one at any time. It enlarges thought beyond that which is known to the horizon of the possible, to new possibilities that are not, and cannot be, known in advance, nor aroused in accordance with specific guidelines or rules. To think new thoughts is, therefore, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), to engage in experimenting with that which is actual, the shapes, lines, colours, moves that are already in place. It is to destabilise them. It is to move in unforeseen ways, not necessarily limited by present and historical states. It is to actualise that which is not and cannot be known beforehand; it is, for Deleuze, to become “someone who creates [his or her] own impossibilities, and thereby creates possibilities” without which we would not “have the line of flight, the exit that is creation” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 133). To think is therefore “to create—there is no other creation—but to create is first of all to engender ‘thinking’ in thought” (Deleuze, 1994, p. 185). Without thinking we are lost, reduced to objects of destructive forces, which limit, even triumph over us and our possibilities. Without thinking we give in to circumstances that make us slaves or move us in misleading directions. We give up the originality of thought, and diminish our ability to be creative and to engage “in new, perhaps previously unimagined, modes of thinking” (Jeanes, 2006, p. 128). In order to combat such destructive forces, we should, engage in thinking, which is territorial, that is, placed in various moves or ways of life; thinking leads us to encounter both active and reactive forces, which for Deleuze, is a “fundamental *encounter*” (Deleuze, 1994, p. 176), one which can deterritorialise us in relation to the various embedded ways of thought and fuel the “passion to think” (p. 176), and as such can open the possibility to recapture that which is lost, and help us to find our way anew.

Thinking is, therefore, always dangerous. It means, for Deleuze and Guattari (1994), “to follow the witch’s flight” (p. 41) and move from that which is known to the unthought. It leads us to experiment without predetermined or fixed ends, and is as such “an art of living” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 111). To move between perceptible becomings and becoming imperceptible through thinking is therefore to “head for the horizon, on the plane of immanence, and ... [to] return with bloodshot eyes, yet they are the eyes of the mind” (Deleuze and Guattari, 1994, p. 41). It leads us to “cross the line, and make it endurable, workable, thinkable” (Deleuze, 1995, p. 111). Such thinking is a real possibility, although sometimes it is overwhelmed, even triumphed over, by reactive forces.

¹ See Fredrika Spindler (2011) for a discussion on Deleuze and the event, and on how events can create cracks in that which is known so that lines of flight can be created to that which is not yet known.

It can lead us away from a narrow focus on active forces, the one-sided views on affirmation, joy and happiness and dead-end utopias, to an encounter with both active and reactive forces, the impact of capitalism on the formation of our images, as well as to a real affirmation of the indefinite individuality of life, which when it happens is hard work.

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